

Copper and Silver Catalysed Oxidation of Glycinatopentaaminocobalt(III) by Potassium Perdisulphate

ANADI C. DASH, RABINDRA K. NANDA* and PRAKASH MOHANTY

Department of Chemistry, Utkal University, Bhubaneswar-751 004

The kinetics of oxidation of glycinatopentaaminocobalt(III) ion was investigated at 60° and 1 mol dm⁻³ perchlorate medium. The reaction is first order in [complex] and fractional order (0.5) in [peroxydisulphate]. Slight rate retardation is observed when [H⁺] increases from 0.1 to 0.7 mol dm⁻². The products of the reaction are Co^{II}, HCHO, CO₂ and NH₄⁺. The reaction is catalysed by Ag^I and Cu^{II}. It is presumed that these catalysts produce species of their higher oxidation states which are more effective than peroxydisulphate. Increase in rate constants in presence of catalysts under nitrogen atmosphere is observed.

THE kinetics of metal ion catalysed peroxydisulphate oxidation of amino acids has been studied¹⁻³ from kinetic stand point. In this paper we report the kinetics of peroxydisulphate oxidation of coordinated glycinate (oxygen bonded) in (NH₄)₅CoGlyH³⁺ in the presence of Ag^I and Cu^{II} ions under varying conditions.

Experimental

Potassium peroxydisulphate, perchloric acid, sodium sulphate, copper sulphate and silver nitrate were of B.D.H., A.R. grade Glycinatopentaaminocobalt(III) perchlorate was prepared by the reported method⁴. The reaction was studied under pseudo-first order conditions and the reaction was monitored by following the decrease of absorbance due to the complex with time at 500 nm using a Beckman DU2 spectrophotometer. The pseudo-first order rate constants were calculated from slopes of log (A_t-A_∞) vs time plots. Rate of production of Co^{II} was also followed by Kitson's method⁴.

Results and Discussion

- (i) The kinetic results can be summarised as follows.

The reaction was found to be fractional order (0.5) in [oxidant]. A plot of k_{obs} (Table 1) vs [oxidant]^{1/2} was linear at constant [Ag⁺] and [Cu²⁺].

- (ii) Under pseudo-first order condition, i.e. [oxidant]=0.02 mol dm⁻³, [H⁺]=0.1 mol dm⁻³ and [catalyst]=10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ the reaction followed first order kinetics in [complex]. Under these conditions, the first order rate constants remained constant (0.64 × 10⁻⁴ s⁻¹) at different initial [complex] in the range 0.004 to 0.006 mol dm⁻³ using Cu^{II} ion as catalyst.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING [OXIDANT] ON RATE OF OXIDATION OF COORDINATED GLYCINATE IN (NH₄)₅CoGlyH³⁺ IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM

[HClO₄]=0.1 mol dm⁻³, Ionic strength=1 mol dm⁻³, [complex]=0.004 mol dm⁻³, Temp.=60°

10 ⁴ [AgNO ₃] mol dm ⁻³	[K ₂ S ₂ O ₈] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁴ k _{obs} s ⁻¹	10 ⁴ [CuSO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁴ k _{obs} s ⁻¹
1.0	0.018	0.680	1.0	0.590
1.0	0.020	0.760	1.0	0.690
1.0	0.030	0.840	1.0	0.727
1.0	0.040	0.900	1.0	0.729
1.0	0.050	0.940	1.0	0.806

- (iii) The rate constant decreased with the increase in [H⁺]. For example, under the conditions [complex]=0.004 mol dm⁻³, [oxidant]=0.02 mol dm⁻³, [catalyst]=10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³, I=1 mol dm⁻³, and [H⁺]=0.1 to 0.7 mol dm⁻³, 10⁴k_{obs} decreased from 0.64 to 0.50 s⁻¹ for Cu^{II} catalysed reaction and 0.77 to 0.52 s⁻¹ for Ag^I catalysed reaction.
- (iv) Pseudo-first order rate constants were determined at various [catalyst]. The plot of rate constants against different [catalyst] was linear (Fig. 1). Rate constants at different initial [catalyst] are given in Table 2. k_{obs} vs [Mⁿ⁺], (Mⁿ⁺=Ag⁺ or Cu²⁺), plot was linear upto 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ for Cu^{II} catalysed reaction and upto 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ for Ag^I catalysed reaction. The order in [Ag⁺] became greater than one at [Ag⁺]>10⁻² mol dm⁻³.
- (v) Rate constants followed by measuring decrease of [Co³⁺]_T and increase of [Co²⁺] were 0.64 × 10⁻⁴ and 0.63 × 10⁻⁴ s⁻¹ when [complex]=0.004 mol dm⁻³, [Cu²⁺]=10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³, [oxidant]=0.02 mol dm⁻³, [H⁺]=0.1 mol dm⁻³, I=1 mol dm⁻³ and temp. 60°. When the same experiments were conducted with Ag^I as catalyst the rate constants were 0.77 × 10⁻⁴ and 0.75 × 10⁻⁴ s⁻¹, respectively.

Fig. 1. $10^4 k_{\text{obs}} \text{ s}^{-1}$ vs $[M^{n+}] \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{complex}] = 0.006 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{HClO}_4] = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] = 0.08 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. A, $[M^{n+}] = [\text{Ag}^+]$ and B, $[M^{n+}] = [\text{Cu}^{2+}]$, all other conditions being the same.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING [CATALYST] ON OXIDATION OF GLYCINATO COMPLEX

$[\text{HClO}_4] = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{oxidant}] = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,
 $[\text{complex}] = 0.004 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{Temp.} = 60^\circ$

$[\text{CuSO}_4]$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ s^{-1}	$[\text{AgNO}_3]$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ s^{-1}
1×10^{-3}	0.88	1×10^{-3}	4.80
5×10^{-4}	0.78	5×10^{-4}	2.46
1×10^{-4}	0.73	1×10^{-4}	0.88
5×10^{-5}	0.68	5×10^{-5}	0.85
1×10^{-5}	0.64	1×10^{-5}	0.77

(vi) The oxidation reaction was studied under nitrogen atmosphere. The value of rate constant when $[\text{Ag}^+]_T = 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}^+] = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{complex}] = 0.004 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] = 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, was $1.02 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ while rate constant of the same reaction in air was $0.77 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

When the same experiment was conducted under nitrogen atmosphere taking copper as catalyst $[\text{Cu}^{2+}]_T = 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the rate constant was $0.85 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$, the corresponding rate constant in air being $0.64 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Enhancement of rate constant under nitrogen atmosphere indicates that oxygen is an inhibitor.

Possible mechanism :

where $R = (\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co}^{3+}$, $\text{OX} = \text{oxidant}$, $M^{n+} = \text{Cu}^{2+}$ or Ag^+ , under pseudo-first order condition of $[\text{oxidant}]_T$ the rate law will be given by equation (1).

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_1[\text{H}^+] + k_2K_1 + k_3K_2K_1[M^{n+}]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_1 + K_1K_2[M^{n+}]} \quad (1)$$

Equation (1) can be linearised to equation (2) for which $k'_{\text{obs}} = k_{\text{obs}}$ at $[M^{n+}]_T = 0$

$$\frac{(k_{\text{obs}} - k'_{\text{obs}})[\text{H}^+] + K_1}{[M^{n+}]K_1} = K_2k_3 - K_2k_{\text{obs}} \quad (2)$$

At a fixed $[M^{n+}]$, $[\text{oxidant}]_T$ and varying $[\text{H}^+]$ the rate data were expressed by equation (2). Value of K_1 is negligible in comparison to $[\text{H}^+]$, so equation (2) can be written as equation (3).

$$(k_{\text{obs}} - a)[\text{H}^+] = b - c k_{\text{obs}} \quad (3)$$

where

$$a = k'_{\text{obs}}, \quad b = K_1K_2k_3[M^{n+}] \quad \text{and} \quad c = K_1K_2[M^{n+}]$$

The plot of $(k_{\text{obs}} - a)[\text{H}^+]$ vs k_{obs} for both Cu^{2+} and Ag^+ (both at $0.0001 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) catalysed reactions were linear (Fig. 2) supporting the proposed mechanism. The values of b and c for copper catalysed oxidation, were found to be $0.15 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $2.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, respectively. The values of b and c for silver catalysed oxidation of the same complex are found to be $0.205 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and 0.25 mol dm^{-3} , respectively.

Fig. 2. $10^4 (k_{\text{obs}} - a) [\text{H}^+] \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ vs $10^4 k_{\text{obs}} \text{ s}^{-1}$. A, AgI catalysed reaction and B, Cu^{2+} catalysed reaction.

The proposed reaction scheme for Ag^+ and Cu^{2+} catalysed oxidation reaction suggests that the

binuclear species are the reaction intermediates. Presumably Ag and Cu in such species exist in 2+ and 3+ states, respectively and induce inner-sphere oxidation of the coordinated glycinate. The observed order of the reaction with respect to $[S_2O_8^{2-}]$ being 0.5, $SO_4^{\cdot -}$ produced from the thermal dissociation of the oxidant $[S_2O_8^{2-} \rightleftharpoons 2SO_4^{\cdot -}]$ appear to be the oxidising species. At high [catalyst] deviation from the linearity of k_{obs} vs $[M^{n+}]$ plot is observed. The greater than first order dependence with respect to $[M^{n+}]$ suggests that presumably more than one catalyst metal ion are involved at higher concentration range. This point requires further study. Activation parameters for the copper and silver catalysed reaction were calculated by determining rate constants at four different temperatures

(45, 50, 55 and 60°) and at $[H^+] = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Ag^+] - [Cu^{2+}] = 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The values of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ for copper and silver catalysed reactions were found to be $42.12 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $-206 \text{ Jk}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, and 28.7 kJ mol^{-1} and $-241 \text{ Jk}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, respectively.

References

1. G. CHANDRA and S. N. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, 11, 773.
2. M. G. RAM REDDY, B. SETHURAM and T. N. BAO, *Indian J. Chem. Sect. A*, 1978, 16, 81.
3. J. FUJITA, T. YASUI and Y. SHIMURA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn*, 1965, 38, 654.
4. R. E. KITSON, *Anal. Chem.*, 1950, 22, 664.